

School-Based Training as Predictor of Learning Organization Skills of Teachers in Matina District, Davao City

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Abstract. The study aimed to investigate the school-based training on the learning organization skills of teachers. The researcher selected 216 elementary school teachers in Matina District in Davao City as the survey respondents in this study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that school-based training was described as extensive while learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City was described as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between school-based training and the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City. Evidently, regression analysis proved that school-based planning, instruction, and management training significantly influenced teachers' learning organization skills in Matina District in Davao City. The researcher recommends that the Department of Education develop policies that incentivize teachers to participate in training and reward them for acquiring new skills and certifications. The study, therefore, was conducted to further utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. school-based training
2. Educational management
3. learning organizational skills of teachers

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1. Introduction

Learning organization is an effort carried out by the person in charge of learning activities in order to achieve optimal conditions so that learning activities can be carried out as expected. The teacher's skills in managing the class is the first step in students' success in achieving good learning outcomes. Teachers' learning organization skills has been highlighted across numerous research studies as a significant variable contributing to successful teacher's delivery of instruction. The most obvious reason for this assertion is that effective classroom management sets the stage for teaching and learning. It sets a tone in the classroom that captures students' attention – as a necessity for effective teaching and learning. More so, effective learning organization skills have been discussed extensively at educational seminars and workshops, with efforts aimed at bringing lasting solutions to the problem of students' poor academic performance encountered in public elementary schools. Therefore, the researcher

deemed it necessary to explore factors such as school-based training that might improve the learning organization skills of teachers. As highlighted by Al-Amarat (2015), in any classroom, regardless of grade level, the potential for conflict is inevitable; thus, learning organization skills and mastering order inside the school are the most critical factors in the educational process and basic requirements. According to Tomlinson and Jarvis (2014), the effective implementation of learning organization such as teaching effectively, rewarding appropriate behaviors, imposing sanctions on inappropriate student behaviors, adapting lessons based on student characteristics, and effective use of the lesson period can increase student achievement and desired behaviors. Moreover, Blazar (2016) reported that effective practices in managing the classroom not only provide a competitive learning environment, but also provides emotional support to the students. This is because when the teacher manages the classroom very well, the teacher gets to know the students, forming positive student-learner relationships that presumably lessen the need for control and become the foundation for all interaction in the classroom (Llego, 2017). On one hand, Tanang (2016) characterized school-based training as the variety of specialized training that develops skills, knowledge, and attributes that are specifically valued by professional associations, organizations, and bodies connected to future careers. Accordingly, school-based training is the set of skills that characterize an individual's skills, knowledge, expertise, and other characteristics as a teacher. Baker (2015) mentioned that school-based training programs for teachers enhance teachers' professionalism, especially by elevating knowledge, skills, and practice in teaching. Consequently, teachers who attend professional development training are much more likely to try new methods of delivering instruction and integrating instructional technology (Twining, Raffaghelli, Albion, Knezek, 2013). On the other hand, separate researches indicate that school-based training and learning organization skills of teachers are important in educational processes. However, those studies were conducted in foreign settings, and the researcher has not yet come across any study determining the relationship between these variables. As an example, the study conducted by Tomlinson and Jarvis (2014) showed that school-based training focuses on improving instructional methods, including innovative teaching techniques, technology integration, and pedagogical approaches. This enhances teachers' ability to create engaging and effective student learning experiences. According to Yildiz (2017), training programs help teachers develop classroom management skills, including behavior and discipline techniques. This leads to a more organized and orderly learning environment conducive to student success. Additionally, the study by Etheridge (2010) found that school-based training ensures that teachers understand and align their instruction with curriculum standards and educational objectives, ensuring that students receive a coherent and comprehensive education. Meanwhile, teachers' ineffective learning organization practices inside the classroom remain an increasing problem for teachers in elementary schools worldwide. Temli –Durmus (2016) reported that in a poorly organized learning environment, students exhibit disruptive behaviors such as sleeping, late coming, noise-making, miscopying of notes, eating, calling nicknames, and verbal or physical threats to fellow learners or the teacher. In addition, Darci Borden (2013) expressed that the teacher's failure to implement effective classroom management can lead to a level of continued frustration that pushes teachers to their breaking point and some extremely frustrated teachers end up leaving the profession. In our very own locality, particularly in Matina District, Davao City, the researchers have noticed that there seems to be a problem with the

learning organization practices of the teachers since the record shows high admission ratings on guidance counseling among students. The record indicates that students are oftentimes engaged in classroom disruptive acts, which resulted in their low performance. Despite all the efforts of the school administration, the high level of absences and admission to guidance counseling due to disruptive behavior among students is steadily increasing. One factor that was observed by the researcher is the poor learning organization skills of teachers, which is due to a lack of training, especially during the pandemic. Although Jones and Dexter (2016) stated that school-based training was linked to the classroom management practices of the teachers. However, this research may not be reliable

since those researchers do not have data for the research, and researchers have not been able to replicate that work. In addition, the researchers took samples from higher education levels. The relationship of these variables may be different if the respondents are from the teachers handling lower grade levels. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine context, particularly in the Matina District, Davao City, using a quantitative research design. Specifically, the researcher made use of a correlational approach to have a better understanding of the relationship between school-based training and the learning organization skills of teachers, which are found to be scarce.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study, the researcher. Quantitative research, as described by Bhandari (2020), is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on the testing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, while, non-experimental research is research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), descriptive-correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause and effect

relationship between variables. In this study, the researcher was able to look into the relationship between variables— school-based training and teachers' learning organization skills. In this connection, the study focused on the relationships among variables for the purpose of determining the significance of the relationship between these variables. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to perform an experiment in a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the elementary school teachers in Matina District, Division of Davao City. The 212 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata.

In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents of the survey. These are as follows: those permanent-regular teachers in Matina District in Davao City; teachers who have participated in school-based training programs focused on professional development, instructional improvement, or classroom management within the past years; teachers not concurrently participating in other studies with similar research objectives to avoid potential data contamination; and teachers who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study used adapted and modified survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. The scaling was done by using one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point or the fair level, with a

uniform interval of 0.80. Also, the survey questionnaires underwent validation by an external and internal panel of experts. The first tool is about school-based teacher training. This questionnaire was adapted from Pan (2004), which has four indicators, namely: planning, instruction, management, and assessment. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.945, which was interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of school-based training of the teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	School-based training of the teachers is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	School-based training of the teachers is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	School-based training of the teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	School-based training of the teachers is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	School-based training of the teachers is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the learning organization skills of teachers Questionnaire adapted from Temli-Durmus (2016) which is divided among three domains namely: management practices, behavioral practices, and instructional practices. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.918 interpreted as excellent, indicating high

reliability and consistency among the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of learning organization skills of teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The learning organization skills of teachers are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The learning organization skills of teachers are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learning organization skills of teachers are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The learning organization skills of teachers are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The learning organization skills of teachers are never manifested.

Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school’s division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Matina District in Davao City. The identified elementary school teachers in Matina District in Davao City were contacted by phone to explain the research study and obtain consent. To preserve the anonymity of the survey, the researcher sent a link to the survey and consent form to principals, and the principals sent out the link to the identified respondents. An explanation of the voluntary study was sent

with the link so that the respondents were fully informed, and if requested, a paper copy was provided. The email explained that the principals of the participants’ schools had granted prior approval. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted last October 10-12, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the study’s respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the school-based training and learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao del Norte. It was used to supply the answers for objectives 1 and 2.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (school-based training) and dependent (learning organization skills of teachers) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usu-

ally denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Linear Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the significant influence of school-based training on the learn-

ing organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of school-based training and learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City; the significant relationship between school-based training and learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City; and the influence of school-based training on the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City.

Summary of School-Based Training in Matina District, Davao City

Lastly, Table 1 shows the school-based training of teachers in Matina District, Davao City. It shows that the overall mean of school-based training of teachers is 3.43, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. This suggests that a comprehensive and intensive strategy, exceeding standard professional development, often provides educators

with detailed and specialized training across various dimensions of teaching and education. This finding supports Schleicher's (2021) assertion that extensive school-based training can foster a culture of excellence, collaboration, and innovation within educational institutions, benefiting teachers and students alike. It presents avenues for continual professional development, allowing teachers to continuously enhance their skills and expertise throughout their careers.

Table 1. Summary of School-Based Training in Matina District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Planning	3.49	Extensive
Instruction	3.62	Extensive
Management	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Assessment	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.43	Extensive

More so, school-based training in terms of instruction acquired the highest mean score of 3.62 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while, school-based training in terms of management got the lowest mean score of 3.28 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers. This suggest that teachers who undergo rigorous training are likely to possess

the skills and knowledge necessary to take on leadership roles within their educational institution. By engaging in comprehensive training programs, educators can develop competencies in areas such as instructional design, assessment, and educational leadership, which are essential for assuming leadership responsibilities. This aligns with Baker's (2015) perspective that teachers who undergo extensive training may be

more equipped to assume leadership responsibilities within their educational institution, thereby fostering the growth of the broader educational community.

Summary of Learning Organization Skills of Teachers in Matina District, Davao City

Lastly, Table 2 presents a summary of the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City. The table indicates that the overall mean score for these skills is 3.32, reflecting a moderately extensive level. This suggests that teachers sometimes manifested these learning organization skills. The

finding suggests that teachers utilize proficient practices that are not overly specialized but are well-suited for fostering a positive learning atmosphere. This observation aligns with Nasey’s (2012) argument that teachers with moderate-level learning organization skills effectively involve students in the learning process, leading to active participation and a keen interest in academic endeavors. These skills play a vital role in establishing a generally positive and supportive learning environment, where students feel secure, valued, and motivated to engage in learning.

Table 2. Summary of Learning Organization Skills of Teachers in Matina District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Management Practices	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Behavior Management	3.44	Extensive
Instructional Management	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.32	Moderately Extensive

Adding more, results in Table 9 show that learning organization skills of teachers in terms of behavior management acquired the highest mean score of 3.44 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, learning organization skills of teachers in terms of instructional management acquired the lowest mean score of 3.24 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested among teachers. The result indicates that teachers with moderate-level instructional management skills effectively establish a supportive and structured classroom environment conducive to learning. However, their approach may lack the innovative and advanced techniques that could lead to exceptional student achievements. This aligns with Llego’s (2017) notion that possessing a moderate level of instructional management facilitates moderate enhancements in student learning outcomes. While these practices contribute to maintain-

ing a stable learning environment, they may not reach the highest standards of innovation and excellence.

Relationship Between School-Based Training and Learning Organization Skills of Teachers in Matina District, Davao City

The results of the analysis of the relationship between school-based training and the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that school-based training has a significant positive relationship with the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.462, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of school-based training changes, learning organization skills of teachers also changes

significantly. Adding more, results on the table shows that school-based training in terms of planning; instruction; management; and assessment have significant positive relationship with the learning organization skills of teachers with

a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.330, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.413, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.352, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.562, p < 0.05$), respectively.

Table 3. Relationship Between School-Based Training and Learning Organization Skills of Teachers in Matina District, Davao City

Variables	Learning Organization Skills	r-value	p-value
Planning	0.330*	0.000	Reject H0
Instruction	0.413*	0.000	Reject H0
Management	0.352*	0.000	Reject H0
Assessment	0.562*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall School-Based Training	0.462*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r < 1.00$;

Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.00 < r < 0.30$;

No Correlation for $r = 0.00$

This shows that school-based training initiatives focus on empowering teachers with a diverse toolkit of instructional strategies and techniques. By incorporating innovative teaching methods and integrating technology into their lessons, teachers can create dynamic and engaging learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students. The finding supports the idea proposed by Tomlinson and Jarvis (2014) that school-based training prioritizes the enhancement of instructional practices, encompassing innovative teaching methodologies, technology integration, and pedagogical approaches. This concerted effort aims to equip teachers with the skills necessary to develop captivating and impactful learning experiences for their students. Additionally, the result is in line with Etheridge’s (2010) research, which emphasized that school-based training ensures teachers possess a clear understanding of cur-

riculum standards and educational goals. This ensures that instructional practices are aligned with the overarching objectives, thereby providing students with a cohesive and well-rounded education.

Influence of School-Based Training on the Learning Organization Skills of Teachers in Matina District, Davao City

The significance of the influence of school-based training on the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 4 shows that when school-based training in terms of planning, instruction, management, and assessment are considered predictors of learning organization skills of teachers, the model is significant, as evident in an F-value of 109.510 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that school-based training predicts the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in

Davao City. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.444 indicates that school-based training has contributed significantly to the variability of learning organization skills of teachers by 44.40%. In addition, the table shows that there are domains of school-based training that significantly influence the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City. This table also indicates that school-based training in terms of planning, instruction, and management is significant when the predictors are considered. This means that the extent of learning organization skills of teachers increases by 0.162, 0.293, and 0.112 for each unit increase in school-based training. Thus, this leads to

the rejection of null hypothesis that none of the domains of school-based training that significantly influence the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City. An essential aspect of this endeavor is to determine whether the theories underpinning this study have received validation from the results obtained. As regard to Argyris and Schön's (1978) Organizational Learning Theory, the result supports the idea that school-based training can be viewed as a mechanism for promoting organizational learning by enhancing the skills and capabilities of individual teachers, which in turn contributes to the overall learning capacity of the school as an organization.

Table 4. Influence of School-Based Training on the Learning Organization Skills of Teachers in Matina District, Davao City

School-Based Training	Learning Organization Skills	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Planning	.162*	.151	.046	.000	Reject H0	
Instruction	.293*	.318	.051	.000	Reject H0	
Management	.112*	.323	.047	.000	Reject H0	
Assessment	-.019	.108	.002	.112	Accept H0	
R²	= 0.444					
F-value	= 109.510*					
p-value	= 0.000					

*Significant @ p<0.05

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusion and recommendation. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of school-based training significantly influence learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The re-

searcher selected the 212 elementary school teachers in Matina District in Davao City as the respondents through stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency

of the items in the instrument. School-based training of teachers in Matina District, Davao City was extensive. School-based training of teachers in terms of planning and instruction were also extensive, while, school-based training of teachers in terms of management and assessment were rated as moderately extensive. The learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City, were rated as moderately extensive. Also, the learning organization skills of teachers in terms of management practice and instructional practices were moderately extensive, while the learning organization skills in terms of behavioral practices were rated as extensive. The result showed that school-based training has a significant positive relationship with teachers' learning organization skills. Also, school-based training in terms of planning, instruction, management, and assessment has a significant positive relationship with teachers' learning organization skills. School-based training was found to have contributed significantly to the variability of the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City. School-based training in terms of planning, instruction, and management significantly influenced the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District in Davao City.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: School-based training of teachers in Matina District, Davao City was extensive. This aligns with Schleicher's (2021) argument that comprehensive school-based training has the potential to cultivate an environment of excellence, collaboration, and innovation within educational institutions, which brings benefits to both teachers and students. It provides opportunities for ongoing professional development, enabling educators to continuously improve their skills and knowledge throughout their careers. Learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City was rated as moderately extensive. This suggests that teachers sometimes

manifested these learning organization skills. The discovery indicates that teachers employ effective practices that are not excessively specialized but are appropriate for nurturing a favorable learning environment. This observation is consistent with Nasey's (2012) assertion that teachers with intermediate-level learning organization skills adeptly engage students in the learning process, resulting in active participation and a strong interest in academic pursuits. School-based training has a significant positive relationship with the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City. This means that as the extent of school-based training changes, the learning organization skills of teachers also significantly change. The finding supports the idea proposed by Tomlinson and Jarvis (2014) that school-based training prioritizes the enhancement of instructional practices, encompassing innovative teaching methodologies, technology integration, and pedagogical approaches. This concerted effort aims to equip teachers with the skills necessary to develop captivating and impactful learning experiences for their students. School-based training in terms of planning, instruction, and management are the domains that significantly influenced the learning organization skills of teachers in Matina District, Davao City. This affirmed that the learning organization skills of teachers are a function of school-based training in Matina District, Davao City. The result corroborates with Argyris and Schön's (1978) Organizational Learning Theory indicating that school-based training can be viewed as a mechanism for promoting organizational learning by enhancing the skills and capabilities of individual teachers, which in turn contributes to the overall learning capacity of the school as an organization.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for consideration: The Department of Education may ensure that schools have adequate funding and resources

for training programs, including access to technology, training materials, and expert trainers. Ensuring that schools have sufficient funding and resources for training programs is crucial for the Department of Education. This includes providing access to essential elements such as technology, training materials, and qualified trainers. Adequate funding enables schools to invest in modern technology and equipment, which are essential for effective training sessions. Moreover, access to comprehensive training materials equips educators with the necessary resources to enhance their skills and knowledge. School heads may work with teachers to identify their individual and collective training needs, and tailor training programs accordingly. Collaboration between school heads and teachers was essential in identifying and addressing training needs effectively. School heads play a critical role in understanding the unique requirements of their teaching staff and fostering a culture of professional development within the school. By working closely with teachers, school heads can gain insights into the specific areas where educators require training and support. This collaboration allows for a tailored approach to training programs, ensuring that they address the specific needs and goals of the teaching staff. Teachers may continuously reflect on their teaching practices and seek feedback from peers, mentors, and supervisors. Continuously reflecting on teaching practices and seeking feedback from various sources is a vital aspect of professional growth and development for teachers. By engaging in reflective practices, educators could gain valuable insights into their teaching methods, instructional strategies, and classroom management techniques. Reflective practice involves critically analyzing teaching experiences, identifying areas of strength and areas for improvement, and making adjustments to enhance teaching effectiveness. Future researchers may investigate how training programs can be designed to address equity issues, ensuring that all teachers have access to quality training opportunities. They should also identify and disseminate best practices in school-based training, highlighting the most effective approaches for improving teacher skills.

5. References

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